

Middle East University

Faculty of Education

FACTORS THAT CONTRIBUTE TO MIDDLE AND HIGH SCHOOL
STUDENTS' ACADEMIC MOTIVATION AND ACHIEVEMENT
IN THE UNITED ARAB EMIRATES

A Thesis

Presented in Partial Fulfillment of the

Requirements for the Degree

Master of Arts in Education

by

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THESIS ABSTRACT

Master of Arts in Educational Leadership

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Title: FACTORS THAT CONTRIBUTE TO MIDDLE AND HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS' ACADEMIC MOTIVATION AND ACHIEVEMENT IN THE UNITED ARAB EMIRATES

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Academic motivation is the power that moves students to participate in the educational endeavor. Motivation is not simple as it sounds—it is as complex as human consciousness is. Academic motivation can be caused by an intrinsic or extrinsic stimulus, sometimes even both. Recent studies have empirically shown that academic motivation is an essential factor in promoting students' educational achievements. Second language motivation, especially in a bilingual school system, is also vital for students to pursue and acquire a new language. Even though second language motivation shares some factors with academic motivation, still it has its own motivational issues.

This descriptive and correlational study aimed mainly to investigate students' levels of motivation in a government-run school located in a GCC country. Specifically, it looked at academic motivation, English motivation, the relationship between selected demographic variables and students' English grades and overall

academic achievements. Data for this study was obtained from student through a 3 parts questionnaires, and students' actual grades for the current school year were also obtained.

This study means a lot to me, merely because I was a part of the targeted school, as a teacher and student advisor, where I have always suspected that students are not as motivated as they should have been academically, especially when English is the medium of instruction for most of the school subjects.

Sadly, students were not forthcoming in some of the demographic questions that were related to smoking, as well as private tutoring. Also, the statistical results of the data that was gathered have shown that almost all students have high levels of motivations, academically as well as in the English language, while their overall averages were not that good at all.

My personal assumption is that students did not act seriously in answering the motivation question, which prevents me from going further with the analysis of the motivation data. Still, some of the demographic questions, and their academic average as well as their English average proved useful for analysis.

The results of this study show that students living in the city are a better achievers compared to the ones who are living outside the city. Also, students who are living with both parents, or with their mother also are doing better than those who are living with the father, or with someone who is not their parent. Moreover, the study showed a strong correlation (Pearson's $r = 0.91$) between students' averages and their English average, which is an indication of the strong influence of English on their academic achievement, and the need to concentrate on the language prior to the subject matter.

To God be the glory!

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CHAPTER 1

INTRODUCTION

Well-developed countries such as Finland, South Korea, Singapore, and Japan have shown that, despite a scarcity of raw materials, it is possible to develop a strong economy that provides a relatively comfortable and decent lifestyle and long-lasting prosperity for its population. It is no coincidence that the educational system of those countries ranks at the top in the world (Dickinson, 2019), which supports the conclusion that a strong and proper education system is one of the main foundations in bringing about prosperity and progress to any given country in the world.

The newly rich countries of the Arabian Gulf are continuously striving to improve their educational systems by contracting international experts in the field and by allocating a large sum of their yearly budgets toward education. According to the UAE's Information and Services national website (2020), the total investment in education is about 14.8% of the overall federal annual budget. Despite this impressive investment, the educational system is still struggling with obstacles that need to be investigated, in order to implement a proper solution. According to Hanif (2017), some experts in the UAE claim that school curriculums have not been changed in the last 40 to 50 years, and students have been using the same textbooks year after year. Furthermore, a survey of 3500 young locals has shown that almost 50% of them believe that the educational system has failed in preparing them for meeting the job market (Hanif, 2017).

Investment and Dropout

Most of the Arabian Gulf countries have invested heavily in educational systems. The UAE government allocated 10.5 billion Dirhams (an equivalent of 3 billion US dollars) for public schools for the year 2020 (Abbas, 2019). This large allocation of funds illustrates the government's intention to develop the public schooling system. One of their financial investments was joining public school management with a few successful private schools, allowing them to oversee the overall schooling operation by introducing the Public-Private Partnership (PPP) project in 2006. Another vital step in improving the educational system was the usage of the English Language as the main medium for instruction (Al-Issa, 2017).

What is alarming, though, is that up to 25% of boys are dropping out from schools in Dubai alone, while the rate for girls is around 14%, even though the norm in other countries is only around 4% (Ridge et al., 2017). Another fundamental problem is that around 80% of high school graduate students fail to meet the English language proficiency requirements to enter Zayed University, while at the University of Wollongong in Dubai, around 50% of new applicants fail the IELTS or TOEFL exams (Naidoo, 2008). Given the opportunities—even requirements—in English through high school that students are exposed to or get from their teachers or schools, this is a strong indicator that there is a problem.

Based on direct observation from my experience as an educator in the UAE, the average number of students in Grade 6 classrooms was well over 30, but by the time the same students got to 12th grade, there might be as few as 4 students. According to Chaudhary (2013), close to 35% of male students dropped out of school before their senior high school year. Chaudhary suggested that “poor socioeconomic status, family issues, unpleasant school experiences that result in low self-esteem and

underperformance” (para. 4) were some of the reasons behind this phenomenon. Also, according to Ahmed (2011), a study by the Emirates Center for Strategic Studies and Research (ECSSR) linked the high rate of high school dropouts to “uninspiring school environments, lack of interesting, relevant subject options and an absence of counseling” (para. 2).

Factors Associated with Performance

Many studies have observed the challenges facing education in the GCC (Gulf Cooperation Council) Countries and sought to find factors associated with poor performance and school dropout. Factors considered so far include socio-demographics/social characteristics, such as poor family relationships (Önder, 2016), living with one parent, and limited parental guidance (Pulmano, 2017). According to Sarsar (2007), the UAE parents are very proud of their cultural heritage and their native Arabic language, and they are afraid that the school curriculum, which emphasizes introducing foreign knowledge and a foreign language (English), often to the exclusion of Arabic, may be a real threat to their cultural identity. Some studies suggested that socioeconomic status (SES) has a major impact on the educational future of students (Sarsar, 2007). Other studies focused on the schooling system itself, and the negative influence that a school atmosphere had on student outcomes. One study in Qatar (Kamal & Bener, 2009) found that the school’s disciplinary system, the number of students in one class (class size), and teachers’ aggressive attitudes toward students were all indicators of student failure at school.

With all these challenges facing the educational system in the GCC countries, one prime component for academic achievement is motivation, as in other countries. Why is motivation so important, especially in education? Simply because motivation

is an inner driving force/energy that pushes us to act and make a difference in ourselves or the world around us (Souders, 2020).

Academic Motivation

Academic motivation is essential for school success. A student can be intrinsically motivated to study because he/she enjoys acquiring new information, while another student is externally motivated to study because he/she is trying to gain his parents' approval, get passing grades, or gain a reward. According to Chuter (2019), motivation is significant in education because it “fosters creativity and critical thinking, cultivates resilience and self-assurance, and gives a sense of purpose and autonomy in striving after one’s goals” (p. 4).

On the other hand, students, even the ones who are intrinsically motivated to study can be demotivated due to many external factors. Students who are using a foreign language as the main medium of instruction can become demotivated due to factors related to teachers’ qualifications, the school system, and students’ abilities. These factors include problems with the “(a) teaching profession, (b) curriculum, (c) working conditions, (d) students and their parents, (e) colleagues and school administrators, and (f) physical conditions” (Aydin, 2012, p. 9).

This complex situation leads me to want to study motivation, language learning, and school success in the Gulf region, especially in UAE. Is motivation a key to better achievement, or reducing school dropout? What other factors are related? What factors are associated with improved school performance in the UAE?

Problem Statement

The rapid economic growth of the United Arab Emirates requires a well-educated local youth to sustain and improve upon this growth. Unfortunately, despite

the significant investments that the government has allocated to the education system, the students are still academically not performing as well as they should, which is reflected in high dropout rates, and low rate of acceptance at universities, as discussed earlier. This study aims to investigate selected factors such as motivation and language ability to assess their potential impact on educational performance in the UAE.

Research Questions

Below are the questions that this study will address.

1. What are the levels of student academic motivation, motivation/demotivation toward learning English (the language of study), and the level of academic achievement during one academic school year? (Descriptive statistics)
2. Are there significant differences in students' motivation to learn English, their academic motivation, and their overall academic achievement, based on selected demographic variables? (ANOVA)
3. Is there a significant relationship between students' level of motivation and overall academic achievement? Between English language motivation/demotivation and academic achievement? (Correlation)
4. What is the best model for academic achievement that can be built using the variables from this study? (Multiple Regression)

Limitations and Delimitations

Due to time and practical realities, this study was delimited to include the results from only one school. This is a limitation, because, though the students are from many places across the UAE, it is still a single environment. Also, the school population is relatively small (116 students) for generalization purposes. Another

major limitation of this study is that the tested population resides in a different county, and the data collection was not monitored by myself. Some of the demographic questions that dealt with smoking and private tutoring may also have been answered inaccurately due to the school's rules that ban these activities. Finally, the method of collecting data by using a survey, while convenient, presumes that students will fill in the answers carefully and honestly. This may not be the case, particularly with language learners who might not be motivated. These limitations urge caution when interpreting the results from this study. Results might not be applicable in other countries, or even in schools that are significantly different from the one under study.

Conceptual Framework

This study will explore three main factors/categories that could be affecting students' academic achievement (see Figure 1). Figure 1 shows the conceptual framework of this study. The first category is the demographic conditions that play a significant role in promoting or demoting students' academic achievement (Ali et al., 2016). The second category is students' motivation/demotivation level and their attitude toward learning through the use of a second language rather than their mother tongue, which may influence their overall academic achievement (Oroujlou & Vahedi, 2011). The third category is the students' academic motivation level, which is regarded as the driving force behind academic achievement (Steinmayr, et al., 2019).

Figure 1. A conceptual framework of factors that contribute to low academic achievement in the UAE.

Key Terms and Abbreviations

- Academic Achievement** Academic Achievement in this study is measured by student's school grades—high grades equal high academic achievement.
- Demotivation** The factor/factors that prevent students from improving their academic achievement.
- ERG** Existence, Relatedness, and Growth. ERG is a psychological theory labeling 3 human needs categories, as proposed by Clayton Alderfer.
- GCC** Gulf Cooperation Council, An economic and political union between Bahrain, Kuwait, Oman, Qatar, Saudi Arabia and the UAE.
- Medwakh** A smoking apparatus that is widely used in the UAE. It is believed that it is 10 times stronger than the average cigarette.
- Motivation** Motivation is what prompts a desire in students to improve their academic achievement.

CHAPTER 2

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Researchers and practitioners (e.g., Covington, 1998; Macmillan, 1979; Keller, 1983) agree that motivation is one of the most important factors in students' academic achievement. Because of this, motivation is a topic that has been researched intensively. In order to have a better understanding of motivation and its effect on students, this literature review focuses on educational motivation and related topics that are important to this study, including academic motivation and second language motivation which will also be reviewed. Both academic motivation and language learning motivation will be researched from international studies, and with special emphasis on any related studies that can be found from the Gulf region.

Motivation

The sun is considered to be the main source of energy for life on our planet. Motivation plays almost the same role in energizing, empowering, and obliging us to act or behave in a certain way. In this study, motivation is key, because motivation plays a significant role in human learning, in which it stimulates and facilitates the students' learning process and promotes a positive learning environment, where the students are active participants. In my personal experience with a group of UAE students, I have found that much of their academic underperformance seemed to be due to students' lack of interest in education, negative attitudes toward learning, and other external factors, such as teaching methods, teacher characteristics, and the

immediate environment that the students are living in, which has a negative effect on students' educational motivation levels.

Definitions of Motivation

In its simplest form, motivation can be defined as

An internal process. Whether we define it as a drive or a need, motivation is a condition inside us that desires a change, either in the self or the environment.

When we tap into this well of energy, motivation endows the person with the drive and direction needed to engage with the environment in an adaptive, open-ended, and problem-solving sort of way. (Reeve, as cited in Souders, 2021, para. 4)

In a broader definition that deals with motivational constructs and their importance, Ryan and Deci (2000) explain that

Motivation concerns energy, direction, persistence and equifinality—all aspects of activation and intention. Motivation has been a central and perennial issue in the field of psychology, for it is at the core of biological, cognitive, and social regulation. Perhaps more important, in the real world, motivation is highly valued because of its consequences: Motivation produces. It is therefore of preeminent concern to those in roles such as manager, teacher, religious leader, coach, health care provider, and parent that involve mobilizing others to act. (p. 69)

It is this idea that motivation produces that makes it so valuable to the field of Business, as well as education—and the others listed here. If someone knew how to create motivation, he/she could be rich and famous. Unfortunately, it is not that simple to accomplish.

Another definition of motivation builds on Deci and Ryan's (2000) ideas, explaining that motivation is always different from one individual to another. Also, the source of motivation can be primitive, such as the motivation to fulfill biological needs, or cognitive, as in fulfilling higher intellectual ones (Brown, as cited in Duta, 2015).

First based on drive theory, motivation stems from basic innate drives, so motivation have been exist since we are born. Second based on hierarchy, motivation is something that comes from individual needs. Third, based on self-control theory, motivation is something that appears if there is opportunity to make someone to make own choices about what to pursue and what not to pursue (self-control). (p. 55)

Motivation is complex, and can have many definitions and variations. Pakdel (2013) defines motivation in five ways, showing some of that complexity.

Definition 1: motivation is the following of factors or a position which compels an individual to carry out specific actions in an organization.

Definition 2: by assumptions, motivation usually means the thing which makes energy and leads it to stable behavior. In a short word, it is a degree and tentional behaviors [sic] which happen in [the] behavioral status of a person.

Definition 3: motivation is a process that starts with a requirement or a physiological or psychological deficiency and the cause of activation of a behavior either to a target or encourager.

Definition 4: motivation is a set of processes that . . . stimulate, [focusing] orientation and maintaining human behavior towards achieving a goal.

Psychologists examine motivation from two sets, intensity and direction. In other words, motivation is a set of forces that cause people to be engaged in a particular behavior and no other behaviors.

Definition 5: motivation in the concept of interest . . . tends to feel more committed to work. Motivation is assumed that the selections can be influenced by human or other living organisms. (p. 241)

With the diversity in these definitions, motivation can be summarized as the invisible force within a person, which could manifest itself through biological, psychological, and neurological needs, and produce a specific action in order to satisfy these needs. We need to keep in mind that not all people react in the same manner, due to many factors, which could include their personal preferences, physical capabilities, cultural background, or the environment that they are living in.

Motivation Theories

The prominent Greek Philosopher Plato is someone I consider to be a pioneer in motivation, and its power to move people. He was one of the first scholars who thought of motivation as a necessity and categorized three main factors that motivate humans to behave: a) the human appetite, which Plato considered to be a primitive impulse, b) the human spirit, which is the desire for preservation, c) human reasoning, which is our ongoing quest for the ultimate truth (Wright, 2012).

On the other hand, one of the well-known theories of motivation is Maslow's hierarchy of needs, which is based on 5 levels of human needs; once the lowest level is satisfied, people move up the to a higher one (McLeod, 2020). In a simplified manner, McLeod (2020) explains the five levels/stages in Maslow's hierarchy of needs theory, starting with humans' *Biological and Physiological Needs*, such as air,

food, drink, sleep etc., followed by *Self-Preservation Needs*, such as security, stability and protection from nature's elements (cold, rain, floods and fire). Once these needs are fulfilled, humans aim at *Love and Belongingness Needs*, such as having friends, finding love, and having strong relationships in their environs, after which is *Esteem Needs*, where humans aim to build a good reputation for themselves, by mastering a profession, which entitles them for a reputable status and respect in society, and boost their self-esteem. The final level in Maslow's theory is *Self-Actualization Needs*, which is the ultimate level of needs. In this level a person strives to achieve self-actualization, self-fulfillment and the peak of his/her personal growth (McLeod, 2020).

Despite its simplicity and currency, however, there is always a flaw in almost any theory in the world. Theories are not pure facts. Most have profound logical gaps. Kammar (n.d.), articulated some of the gaps in Maslow's hierarchy of needs theory. For instance, he says that humans by themselves are so complex and divergent from each other, and each person has his/her own uniqueness, which makes it safe to say that each person has his/her own priority of needs to fulfill. The simplest example for that is when a mother deprives herself of her own biological needs to satisfy her children's needs instead (the mother denied her level one and two and jumped to level three). Or in the case of Mahatma Gandhi, he deprived himself of the lower needs and went straight to self-actualization. Kammar (n.d.) suggested that any particular human need can cause a totally different reaction/behavior in different person, which could be due to his/her own background, experience, religious beliefs, and so on. Kammar (n.d.) believes that self-actualization for one person is not the same as for another, due to the complexity of human nature.

Building on Maslow's hierarchy of needs, Alderfer (as cited in Carrier, 2019), proposed the ERG Theory which is based on empirical studies on human needs and desire satisfaction, where Alderfer categorized the human needs into three sections: existence needs, relatedness needs, and growth needs. Alderfer also proposed that in case a person could not reach a higher need, he/she will invest more effort into the lower category need (Yang et al., 2011).

Carrier (2019) suggested that Alderfer's ERG Theory is a replica of Maslow's Theory in which Alderfer reorganized Maslow's five categories into three (see Figure 2). Therefore, he argues that it shares the same merits and critiques.

Douglas McGregor introduced Theory X and Theory Y of motivation, which are a prominent motivation theory that is related to the workplace. In an academic setting, it could be compared to studying as a job/work that the students have to perform (Juneja, 2015). According to Cunningham (2011), McGregor Theory X assumes that people have innate dislike for work and will do their best to avoid doing any work, and must be constantly coerced into doing an honest day's job, in which the only reason for coming to work is to collect the pay check. This means that employees must be controlled and threatened to perform. Such an employee needs to be managed, avoids responsibility, and prefers security and will not venture outside his circle of safety. On the other hand, McGregor's Theory Y assumes that employees like to work, which, from their point of view, is something natural, essential to do, and potentially enjoyable and a positive experience. This suggests that people can perform their duties without the usage of punishment or arbitrary control. Rather, the best method for motivating people is by bringing a feeling of commitment to their duties. The most significant motives that a person needs at work are the things that bring up the person's ego and fulfill their self-actualization needs. People are born

with a sense of responsibility, however, it could be diminished due to past experiences (Cunningham, 2011).

Figure 2. Commonality between Maslow’s Hierarchy of needs, and Alderfer’s ERG model.

Note. From *Alderfer’s ERG Theory of Motivation: A Simple Summary*, by J. Carrier, 2019, <https://worldofwork.io/2019/02/alderfers-erg-theory-of-motivation/>

Another well-known theory is Herzberg’s Two-Factor Theory (Motivation and Hygiene Factors), in which Herzberg concluded, after interviewing 200 engineers and accountants all over the USA, that there are two main factors that define employee performance and attitude toward their job. The first factor is Motivation, in which employees are intrinsically involved in their job activities, and this will spur them to

self-satisfactory moods. Hygiene factors, on the other hand, are the second factor that influence performance. Hygiene comes from external sources, such as financial gain, the fear of punishment, or obligations to someone or something. In these cases, the job by itself is not satisfactory to the person, and he/she is extrinsically driven to do it (Yusoff et al., 2013). However, according to Yusoff and colleagues (2013), “most of the research findings across a variety of countries and industries have concluded that Extrinsic (Hygiene) factors have impacted their respondents’ job satisfactions” (p. 21).

No matter how we define motivation, the bottom line is that we all, as humans, have needs to be fulfilled. Students are not immune to those needs. Their biological, emotional and social needs must be met in order to be educated properly. Also, it is safe to say that different cultures have different motivation factors and needs, and the UAE is no exception to the rule. It is vital to understand what makes that culture tick so that we know better how to deal with the UAE youth in motivating them toward academic success.

It is said that you can tell a lot about a child’s character by understanding his/her parent’s characteristics: *the apple does not fall very far from the tree*. It is also true in regard to the motivational forces that move parents—they could manifest themselves in their children’s motivation towards education. In a study by Banerjee (2016), on what factors motivate GCC citizens while working in the banking sector, he claims that Emiratis in general lack working motivation, which has led to banks being extensively operated by expatriates. In an attempt to nationalize most of the jobs in the UAE, especially the banking field, “the UAE government had spent 21% of the Federal budget, to fund various educational and employment initiatives to support the UAE nationals” (p. 64). This has had minimal effect due to the majority of

the UAE's lack of motivation to join the working force. Banerjee's (2016) study establishes that the UAE workers are not motivated by external incentives (extrinsic motivation), such as higher salary, end of year bonus, or rewards. Instead, they are motivated intrinsically, especially when they have deeper and more personal relationships in their work environment, which transcends the dull, robotic, and emotionless working relationship which exists in many work places. This factor may also apply in academic motivation, which is what we will explore next, which will include the impacts of family, environment, and relationships on students' motivational levels.

Academic Motivation

Establishing that basic biological and emotional needs in students must be satisfied as a minimum requirement prior to any actual learning procedures is just the tip of the iceberg. Many other factors play a major role in students' motivational levels, such as their personal goals, aptitudes, cognitive abilities, obligations, persistence, self-efficacy, self-actualization, intrinsic/extrinsic regulators, and so on. These aspects of academic motivation will be defined and summarized in this section, along with related research studies exploring their effects on motivation and performance.

Definitions of Academic Motivation

In a definition that is mostly student-centered, Rowell and Hong (2013) suggest that motivation to learn is the driving force that pushes students (if it manifests itself) to excel in their education or to decline, and eventually fail in their educational struggle if they are demotivated, as in any aspect of life.

Academic motivation refers to the cause of behaviors that are in some way related to academic functioning and success, such as how much effort students put forth, how effectively they regulate their work, which endeavors they choose to pursue, and how persistent they are when faced with difficulties (Usher & Morris, 2012, para. 1). Usher and Morris emphasize the student's efforts and persistence as pursuing and achieving one's goals in education.

In a similar fashion, McGrew (2008) defines academic motivation as a student's desire regarding academic subjects, which is reflected in the way the student approaches education, as well as his/her persistence in pursuing academic accomplishments, and the level of interest toward education. Here McGrew (2008) adds another significant factor to educational motivation, which is goal setting, and intrinsic motivation in the form of interest toward motivation, which are facilitators of academic success.

In a broader and much wider definition, Williams and Williams (2011) define academic motivation as "a motivating force, stimulus, or influence; incentive; drive; something that causes a person or student to act and the expenditure of effort to accomplish results" (p. 2). Williams and Williams (2011) suggest that there are five key ingredients that influence student motivation, starting with the student's self-image, cognitive capabilities, interests and goals, followed by the teacher's characteristics, the school curriculum, the learning process/method and the environment where the student is living. Building on ideas similar to Usher and Morris's (2012) and McGrew's (2008) definitions, Williams and Williams (2011) add other significant constructs for academic motivation such as the curriculum, the teacher's characteristics, and the teaching methods, to give a complete picture of the ultimate factors in academic motivation.

While identifying key components that affect student motivation, Rowell and Hong (2013) categorized academic motivation into five modules:

a) *Beliefs* in one's abilities, or "self-efficacy," which is an essential construct of success, and the stronger the person believes in his/her own abilities to succeed, the better are the chances that he will.

b) *Goals* that students are inspired to achieve, such as joining a well-known university which can be "short term (proximal goals) or long term (distal goals) with a few sub-goals that can be used to assess progress toward a final goal" (p. 160), and play the part of a compass for a ship at the sea; no matter how good the ship is, without the compass, there is a big possibility of being lost at sea.

c) Understanding the *value* of what one is doing is another vital factor that drives us to succeed: this is often called the "what's in it for me."

d) *Intrinsic* motivation that comes from within and from the student's will and desire to achieve, and is considered to be the highest level of motivation, due to the fact that it is self-driven and does not need an external stimulus to sustain it.

e) *Extrinsic* motivation which is created by external stimulation, which could be driven by the need to please their parents or teachers, to get the acceptance of their fellow students, to impress someone that they like at school, to have a better job, and so on. This type of motivation is also vital, but it needs lots of nurturing from teachers, parents and society as a whole.

This last definition in particular is closest to what this study is trying to accomplish by investigating if students are intrinsically or extrinsically motivated, and the role of social and cultural beliefs and how they affect motivation levels.

The Importance of Motivation in Education

The application of motivational theory in education is of utmost importance for the educational family, due to its capabilities to bring learning to students as efficiently as possible. Even though the word *motivation* seems to be simple and straightforward, it can be as complex and confusing as the human consciousness. The same can apply to its theories. “Why is motivation so important for learning success? It is the key to persistence and to learning that lasts. The challenge is to help each person clarify his or her important purposes and then to find, or create, the combination of educational experiences that lead to those desired outcomes” (Chickering & Kuh, 2005, p. 1).

Achievement motivation has the effect of empowering and guiding students' performance toward success and is identified by many scholars as an essential construct of academic success. Chickering and Kuh (2005) suggest that academic achievement motivation cannot be summed up in one factor, rather it includes diverse aspects such as students' confidence in achievements, outcome benefits compared to their effort, whether it meets their goals, their cognitive competence, and so on.

Academic Motivation Theories

Academic motivation theories are a part and an extension of the motivation theories, in which they adapt the motivation theories and build on them to fit the context of students' academic motivation. In this part, I will be discussing some of the important theories that are related specifically to education.

Before looking at academic motivation theories, however, a deeper look at intrinsic and extrinsic motivation factors is crucial, due to their importance in educational motivation. Legault (2016) suggested that human motivation, for students, as well, is basically divided into intrinsic and extrinsic forms. 1) *Intrinsic motivation*

is when students engage in school activities because they are enjoyable, fun, challenging, self-enriching, and self-satisfaction is mostly the main goal behind participating.

2) *Extrinsic motivation* is the opposite of intrinsic, in which students are joining the classroom activities due to external factors or incentives, such as rewards, good grades, pleasing their parents. Extrinsic motivation is often seen as a “necessary evil” to initiate learning progress through the habit of an extrinsic stimulus which occurs regularly. Legault (2016) claimed, though, that those extrinsic motivation experiences will eventually undermine intrinsic motivation for that activity. He argued that “the use of incentives and rewards to motivate people decreases the likelihood that genuine interest and self-generated motivation will develop and persist” (p. 2). It is safe to say that the implementation of extrinsic regulator/s in educational motivation is best presented with the utmost caution due to its double-edged effect on students’ genuine, intrinsic motivation.

One of the well-known theories which took almost half a century of empirical methods to validate is self-determination theory (SDT), which assumes that, no matter what their gender, economic status, cultural background or nationality, all students are equally born with inherent tendencies to grow (Reeve, 2012). Reeve (2012) suggests that what makes SDT unique is the concentration on students’ inner motivational resources as the key factor in facilitating his engagement in the educational process. This is what all students possess and it is the teachers’ role to activate and nurture these resources during every class session.

Reeve (2012) explained that SDT is actually composed of 5 mini-theories (see Figure 3). My study deals extensively with this diversity of regulators and includes most of these essential motivational theories. The 5 theories are explained as follows:

- a) Basic need theory: Relies on autonomy, competence, and relatedness and plays a role in activating student's involvement in the educational process.
- b) Organismic integration theory: This theory discusses four extrinsic regulations:
 - 1. External regulation, where students are after a reward or trying to avoid punishment, which is the "least autonomous type of extrinsic motivation" (p. 155).
 - 2. Introjected regulation, where student get involved due to a feeling of guilt toward disappointing their parents, or to avoid being ashamed and/or pressured at school or by society.
 - 3. Identified regulation, which is extrinsic motivation, but in which a student views the goal as a necessity and puts genuine effort behind attaining it.
 - 4. Integrated regulation, which is when a student pursues a task that he/she really doesn't enjoy but knows that in the end, is needed to achieve a higher purpose, such as studying math, even though he/she does not enjoy it, knowing that it will lead to becoming an engineer.
- c) Goal contents theory: Created to investigate what students strive to attain while studying, and what is their goal for participating in a class.
- d) Cognitive evaluation theory: Explains the effects of two aspects on external factors—*controlling aspects* (students are forced toward a specific behavior), and *informational aspects* (students are encouraged).

- e) Causality orientation theory: Specifies two types of student orientation, one relies on their own interest and personal goals, while the other is a follower and waits for directions.

Self-Determination Theory is almost holistic in the way it includes most of the well-recognized theories on motivation. It is also imperative in my study while dealing with identified, integrated, introjected, and external regulators, which will be used in my surveys that investigate students' motivation toward learning and studying in the English language. Figure 3 explains a bit more deeply the way each of these five aspects of SDT work together to explain motivation. By applying the SDT theory in this study, we can investigate the true interest of the UAE students toward the English language and what drives them to participate in learning it, or what pushes them away from it.

Another key factor and source of motivation in academic achievement, which The study is trying to investigate is self-efficacy. According to Lopez-Garrido (2020), psychologist Albert Bandura was the first professor to introduce the term "self-efficacy," which he used to measure how well a person can perform in dealing with a prospective situation. Self-efficacy can be defined as what a person/student imagine, him/herself is capable of, it is the inner believe/confidence in their own capacity to achieve any task at hand, high self-efficacy will empower a person to employ his/her intrinsic abilities toward achieving his/her goal (Flammer, 2001).

Figure 3. A diagram showing the five mini-theories of Self-Determination Theory.

Note. From A self-determination theory perspective on student engagement, by Reeve, J., 2012, in, L. Christenson, L. Reschly, & C. Wylie (Eds.), *Handbook of Student Engagement*, p. 152: Springer.

Due to its importance in boosting students' achievements, self-efficacy must be cultivated in a person through 1) Mastery experiences, which refers a person's self-efficacy being promoted by taking new challenges and of course succeeding in them, it is like the saying "practice makes perfect." 2) Vicarious experiences, which help in gaining self-efficacy by watching experts who complete tasks successfully. 3) Social persuasion, where participants receive encouragement while undertaking a difficult task. This will definitely boost one's self-efficacy levels, and even though social persuasion might work on any age, it is preferable to start early on in one's life. 4) Emotional and physiological states, in which the person's psychological, physical and emotional conditions have a strong influence on their personal abilities in some particular situation and might hinder their self-efficacy, thus, by learning how to manage anxiety and improve temperament while facing puzzling tasks, individuals may recover their self-efficacy (Lopez-Garrido, 2020) (see Figure 4).

In my study, I am assuming that a low level of self-efficacy among UAE's students is one of the factors behind the low academic achievement, and hopefully by the end of this study, I can have a better idea of the actual level of self-efficacy, as well as its relationship to academic achievement.

In an attempt to develop a theory that might summarize most of the second language motivation theories, Anderman and Leake (2005) came up with some sort of a sum-up theory for educational motivation which includes three essential parts: a) the need for Autonomy (a sense of personal control as the central fact in achievement motivation, "Locus of control, Self-regulation and Self-determination"), b) the need for belonging (humans possess an innate need for relatedness and attachments "social-cognitive theory"), and c) the need of competence (a strong self-assurance that they

are capable of accomplishing the task at hand “Expectancy beliefs, Goal Setting, Attribution, Self-concept and Self-efficacy”).

Figure 4. A diagram showing the 4 factors to improve self-efficacy.

Note. From *A Quasi-Experimental Intervention to Improve Self-Efficacy for Eating and Exercise Weight Management: Short-Term Effects*, by R. Lee, (2013), p. 2. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/234840074_A_Quasi-Experimental_Intervention_to_Improve_Self-Efficacy_for_Eating_and_Exercise_Weight_Management_Short-Term_Effects

In the same manner, Perumal (2009) placed Educational motivation theories into four categories: a) *Behavioral*, introduced and developed by Pavlov, Watson, and Skinner, who claim that students can be conditioned by an operant followed by reinforcement and or punishment. b) *Humanistic*: introduced by Maslow, Murphy, and Rogers, which is based upon the idea that we all are born good, students motive follows Maslow’s hierarchy of needs, once the bottom one is fulfilled, it goes to the next level. Also, our interaction with students should be based on reason, compassion

and students should develop a strong critical thinking. c) *Cognitive*: based on Jean Piaget's cognitive theory, which is basically what level of self-confidence a student has, and what will he/she expect to get in return. d) *Social learning*: students should set and pursue a goal that is challenging, meaningful, intrinsically motivating and reachable.

There are many more motivational theories that deal with education, which are impossible to cover in this literature review. A taste of the more important theories such as Goal Setting Theory by Locke and Latham in the nineteen eightieth, where they advocated that a person is motivated toward participating in an activity in which they have a certain goal in mind that they are trying to attain, and these goals has a significant influence on students' involvement and performance in the learning process (Locke & Latham, 1991). Locke and Latham (1991) argue that there are two types of goals in education: 1) Mastery Goals, in which the student's main goal is to improve his/her proficiency, understanding in the subject that is taught, and to master new skills for his/her self-satisfaction. 2) Performance Goals, in which the main goal in participating in the educational process is gain acceptance (performance-approach) or avoid punishment/ridicule (performance-avoidance). Goals are important because students joining schools without a personal purpose will be aimlessly maneuvering in their educational endeavors and most probably will invest minimal effort in that direction, which could lead to low achievement even though the students may be gifted.

Studies in Academic Motivation

As much as we wish to have one straight answer to any given question, the truth of the matter is totally different. We cannot assume that all students around the world are faced with the same problems, motivated by the same factors, and view the

importance of education the same way. That is why it is essential to investigate some of the studies that are related to the Arabian Gulf context, or a similar environment in order to have a better understanding in regard to their academic motivation situation. Seeking out a better understanding on the factor/factors that affects students' motivational levels in the GCC countries, A study was conducted on middle and high school students in the United Arab Emirates by Khamis and Dukman (2008), taking into account the uniqueness of the UAE youth environment. Their study established that 1) Motivation to learn for males was 30.41, while for females it was 33.63, which is a clear indicator that the UAE female students are a little more academically motivated than males. "There is a significant difference between boys and girls in educational motivation (girls had a higher level of motivation to learn than boys did)" (p. 195). 2) There was a positive correlation between students' motivational levels and small family size, "Students with a small size family are more educationally motivated than students with a large family size" (p. 195). 3) "Students' interest in learning (the highest effect of 32.2%), teacher-student relationship and curriculum content had a significant effect on UAE middle and high school students' motivation in learning" (p. 198). Even though my study is not about different gender motivation factors, still it is interesting to know that family size, teachers' relationship with the students, and the curriculum as a whole has a strong effect on UAE students' motivation.

Intelligence is a strong indicator of academic achievement, but without the proper motivation, intelligent students might be faced with academic failure or even school dropout, whereas high motivation is responsible for lower rates of school dropouts, and higher levels of student academic achievement (Halawah, 2006). Teachers' main goal should be the development of intrinsic motivation in their

students (Halawah, 2006). Understanding the importance of academic motivation, family environment/economic status, and student characteristics/attitude in predicting success in education, Halawah (2006) conducted a study on 388 UAE high-school students in Abu to measure motivation, family influence, and student characteristics. She concluded that students' gender had no correlation in the three cases, while family environment, especially the levels of parents' education, had the highest correlation (.59) with student characteristics, which implies that parental influence affects student achievement. Likewise, a high level of correlation (.34) between motivation and student characteristics makes motivation the second most important factor to parents' education. I assume that in this study, parents had a positive influence on students' motivation levels which led to higher motivation, then to enhanced academic achievement.

The ministry of education (MOE) in the UAE has labeled students from public schools whose overall school grade average is over 90% as gifted students. Understanding what motivates gifted students in the UAE could be helpful in transforming those factors to help struggling students. Rahmanian (2009) conducted a study directed to investigate the source of educational motivation (Intrinsic or Extrinsic Motivation) when dealing with gifted students in UAE government schools, and what motivated them to engage in school activities. Rahmanian (2009) concluded that gifted students in the environment are motivated intrinsically as well as extrinsically, and that extrinsic motivation is a powerful factor in nurturing and prolonging intrinsic motivation, as long as it is applied properly. Rahmanian's (2009) study also indicated that teacher's conduct and approaches in teaching those gifted students plays a significant role in sustaining a healthy motivation among the students. Unfortunately, this study indicated that teachers are more concerned about

students' behavior, rather than developing and fostering their cognitive capabilities, and this leads to excess concentration on rewards (external regulators) as the main motivation factor.

In an endeavor to reverse the low-level educational achievement for local UAE students, the government established Model Schools in Abu Dhabi in 1994, and assigned Australian educational experts to initiate some needed changes in the educational policy (Sarsar, 2007). The model schools were well equipped with high-tech equipment, highly qualified teachers from all around the world, and changed the medium of teaching from Arabic to English in most of the subjects to increase exposure to the English language, and only had local Emirati students. In spite of this, the model schools had no tangible, salient improvement, even after more than 12 years of running them (Sarsar, 2007). According to Sarsar (2007), the teachers were the first ones to be blamed, and were coerced to take TOFEL, IELTS and even BULLATS exams which are primarily used to test abilities in English and business, instead of taking the TKT test which can assess teacher's teaching skills. Sarsar (2007) claimed that there are two main problems that needed attention before anything else: a) Students' low level of motivation as the main source of academic achievement, and b) Empowering and involving both students and teachers in the whole teaching process. Studies like this one are key to understanding the population in this current research study, which likewise suffers from low motivation.

Motivation in English as a Second Language

Educational motivation and motivation in English language learning have lots of similarities, yet in the last forty or fifty years, the evolution of English as *lingua franca* has dramatically affected the field of foreign language education. Subsequently the whole teaching and learning process, and new empirical studies have been done to

investigate the motivation factor in English language learning due to its importance in promoting students to excel. Drakulić (2019) advocates that foreign language students who possess a high level of motivation /self-efficacy, and positive attitude toward the learning process will display stronger listening comprehension and verbal capability growth, which leads to excelling in learning and acquiring the target language.

Even though academic motivation and second language motivation have lots in common, still, second language motivation has its own sets of types of motives. Gardner and Krashen (as cited in Hong & Ganapathy, 2017) divided the second language learning motivation factors into two types: *integrative* motivation and *instrumental* motivation. Integrative motivation is when the participants/students are involved in the learning process with an inner desire/goal to integrate with the language culture and to become as part of its society (Mahadi & Jafari, 2012). Learners with such a motive will have a positive attitude toward the language, willing to pursue the learning process endeavor no matter what obstacles they face, and they will be intrinsically motivated toward that goal. Instrumental motivation, where participants/learners are involved in the learning process for an external gain such as finding a better job, being known as a bilingual person, or acceptance in the society (Rozmatovna, 2020). Students with instrumental motivation are less enthusiastic in pursuing the targeted language, and might lose interest easily if the external factor/trigger is gone.

To understand the link between motivation and learning a second language, Dörnyei (1998) claims that motivation is the main drive that pushes students into learning a second language efficiently, and it is the main reason for creating a long-term goal for a foreign language acquisition. Still, Dörnyei (1998) claims that

motivation in second language acquisition is a profoundly complex factor, due to the complex nature of language itself. The complexity of the language comes from being the communication tool that is used in learning, also as an essential part of the person's identity which affects all his/her consciousness activities, and most importantly, language is the prime pillar in organizing and maintaining societies plus the preservation of its culture. That is what makes motivation in foreign language acquisition not quite like the motivation of education.

A pioneer and lead scholar in the field of second language acquisition, Gardner (2007) claimed that motivation in second language acquisition is not exactly like academic motivation. Considering both educational context and cultural context (which involves taking on elements of another culture), he worked extensively with second language motivation. Gardner (2007) declared that there are two constructs of motivation in second language acquisition: 1) language learning motivation, which is reflected in the socio-educational model, which consists of student aptitudes, and their motivation in learning, the milieu model, and the compliance to communicate model, and 2) classroom learning motivation, in which the language acquisition is a means to an end. Gardner (2007) believed that both motivation types are in action in foreign language acquisition. In the UAE, students are interested in the English language due to its use to communicate with the multitude of expatriates in the country, and as a vital tool to earn higher education.

Bilingualism as a Goal for Second Language Learning

One of the motives for a person to acquire a second language is first and foremost to gain bilingual capabilities in two or more languages, so it is important to look closer at bilingualism as the ultimate aim of that person. According to Liddicoat (1991), bilingualism is for someone to have the capability to speak in two languages,

and usually students are most motivated by the desire for immigrating, and social and/or economic conditions. According to Lambert (as cited in Liddicoat, 1991) there are two types of bilingualism: additive and subtractive. Additive bilingualism is when there is a pertinent harmony between both languages and the culture associated with them, and it has a positive effect on the learner. Subtractive bilingualism develops when there is a deep dichotomy and competition between the two language, and it could occur when the second language is taught without the proper support of the student's mother tongue language. This could explain some of the challenges being faced today in the UAE.

According to Hamers and Blanc (as cited in Liddicoat, 1991), bilingual education plans are divided into four programs: 1. Traditional bilingual in which the mother tongue is primarily used to support the transition to the targeted second language; 2. Mono-literate bilingualism where both languages are used in most school activities, but the second/foreign language is used in teaching literacy skills; 3. Partial bi-literate bilingualism (similar to the Lebanese system) where the mother tongue language is primarily used in social and cultural studies, while the second/foreign language is used in technical/scientific subjects; 4. Total bi-literate bilingualism where skill in both languages is developed in all the educational areas. Knowing the two types of bilingualism and the kinds of programs to introduce to the students could help us better understand how to motivate second language learner in a positive and productive way. In the UAE it is not clear yet which of these approaches they want to apply, due to many complications, such as the necessity of maintaining the cultural identity of the UAE students and the preservation of the Arabic language. Most of their programs are based on a trial and error approach.

Second Language Motivation Theories

Many believe that learning, especially a second language, is greatly influenced by students' attitudes toward the English language, age, sex, and living in the country of the target language. Cabiroğlu (2016) conducted a study to test these factors and their effect on language learning motivation and integrative motivation. Before going into details of his research, it is important to mention that according to Cabiroğlu (2016), in 2009, Dörnyei formed a new clarification of integrative motivation entitled "L2 motivational self-system," which was developed to remove the socio-educational models borders (The socio-educational context suggests that second language learners are motivated through wishing to adapt to the behavioral characteristics of the society's language that being acquired). The L2 motivational self-system consist of three features: "Ideal L2 Self: striving to become the best of one's self, eagerness to improve," "Ought-to L2 Self: some sort of self-preservation, out of necessity or obligation based actions/ motivation," "Attitudes towards learning English: mostly related to the learning atmosphere." Cabiroğlu's (2016) research concluded that:

- Students' attitude toward the English language is deeply affected by the teacher, the material presented and past experiences, which leads to either positive or negative L2 motivation levels.
- Young students can learn a second language much better than adults.
- Student's gender does not play a significant role in L2 motivation.
- Living abroad will increase students' L2 motivation and capabilities.
- Student's integrative motivation was significantly high, due to the fact that students' awareness of the importance of the English language which boost their motivation to excel.

Taking into consideration all Cabiroğlu's suggestions about dealing with teaching students a foreign language can improve the teaching process as well as the student learning outcomes. It is important to induce the collaboration of both social backgrounds (native and foreign language) in the learning process.

The road to a better language acquisition is through strong self-confidence, a high self-efficacy, learner's autonomy and lack of language anxiety, which is mostly centered upon the students' self-image (Alrabai, 2014). In his studies, Alrabai (2014) refers to Dörnyei's motivational teaching practice, which is a technique to promote motivation among students. It can be spurred by: a) Arranging a warm and welcoming environment in the classroom, which includes an acceptable relationship between students and the teacher, and building a supportive overall learning atmosphere. b) Coming up with ways to familiarize learners with the culture and ideals of the foreign language.

c) Maintaining and protecting the learners' self-motivation by applying cooperative learning techniques in the classroom and empowering students to promote their self-confidence and build up their self-efficacy. d) Encouraging a positive motivational self-evaluation for themselves.

Alrabai (2014) strongly opines that the teacher plays a significant role in the process of motivating students to excel in learning the English language, although the English language was introduced bit late to the Saudi culture (in the 1950's) and the government played a negative role in promoting the English language in order to protect the Saudi students' mother tongue. The classroom setting where it is taught is teacher-centered instead of student-centered, and there is the next to zero opportunity for the students to practice English language outside the classroom. Also the Saudi

social, religious and political barriers have played a big role in in the low degree of motivation to learn English by the students (Shah et al., 2013).

Gardner, Dörnyei, Kraemer, Krashen and Lambert, to name a few, have introduced important new discoveries in second language learning in recent years. Schütz (2019), discusses Krashen's Theory of Second Language Acquisition which consists of 5 hypotheses;

The Acquisition-Learning hypothesis, which discusses the “acquired system” which is a subconscious process in learning in the same manner that young children learn a language, and “the learned system” which is a formal instruction and it involves a conscious process);

The Monitor hypothesis, in which the learning system performs promotes the role of a language correction monitor in the learner;

The Input hypothesis, which refers to how second language acquisition takes place;

The Affective Filter hypothesis, in which Krashen claims that “learners with high motivation, self-confidence, a good self-image, a low level of anxiety and extroversion are better equipped for success in second language acquisition” (para. 8).

The Natural Order hypothesis, where Krashen proposes that the “acquisition of grammatical structures follows a 'natural order”” (para. 12).

What is especially important about Krashen’s theory in this study is his Affective Filter hypothesis, which shows how important it is for teachers to focus on students’ self-efficacy and self-confidence while acquiring a new language.

In a different approach to introducing a second language, Schütz (2019), discusses Krashen’s point of view toward second language acquisition, which is that learning is less important than acquisition. Krashen (as cited in Schütz, 2019) claims

that comprehensible input is the fundamental and integral component in the process of second language acquisition. In this way, students advance and develop in the targeted language by continuously receiving input from the target language at a higher level than their current level of capability. Moving from the concept of learning the English language into acquiring it is essential in achieving excellence, simply because the students will view the language as a necessity/second tongue language, and will invest heavily in learning it.

After analyzing L2 motivation theories, Shearin (as cited in Qashoa, 2006) identified six factors that impact motivation in learning the English language:

Attitude: a positive approach toward the new language and the overall class atmosphere

Belief about one's self: self-efficacy should be high.

Goals: a profound believe that language learning coincides with one's educational goals.

Involvement: students must participate willingly in the learning activities.

Environmental support: from teachers, parents and peer students.

Personal attributes: Age, aptitude, past learning experiences.

Second language students' self-image is a crucial factor in the process of motivating him/her in pursuing a foreign language, Markus and Nurius (1986, as cited in Cabiroğlu, 2016) suggest "possible selves" in which they have tried to define one's cognitive visions of the future and motivation. These different "selves" emphasize the importance of the person's own dreams, desires and goals in affecting their motives (positively or negatively), which will be reflected in their attitude toward a certain activity. These "possible selves" comes in two different forms:

What they could be: these aims are feasible due to their high self-efficacy, and self-confidence, and usually people will be motivated to conduct any action that is required.

What they want to be: their innate hopes and dreams of becoming better than they are at the moment. Usually, people are a bit reluctant to engage in an activity that requires them to leave their safety zone, and most of them will not invest in reaching their better vision of themselves due to the fear of failure or the lack of self-confidence.

Basically, Markus and Nurius' (1986, as cited in Cabiroğlu, 2016) "possible selves" is essential in L2 self-motivation, because it encourages educators to bring students possible selves from what they are scared to be, to what they want to be and eventually to what could be.

Second Language Motivation Studies

It was a difficult task to find sufficient studies/research regarding second language motivation in the acquisition of the English language among middle and high school students in the United Arab Emirates. Due to that fact I had to introduce studies that included students from elementary schools and higher learning institutes, colleges and universities, as well as from other countries with similar issues to the Arabian Gulf, but the major focus is on Gulf countries.

Motivation in learning a second language is "a combination of an enduring effort to commit to learning, a genuine desire to learn, and a positive attitude toward learning the language" (p. 742), where two factors are essential for the formation of motivation: educational context and cultural context (Gardener, as cited in Khansir, et al., 2016). Understanding the effects of the socioeconomic status of the learner, the motivation level toward the language learning, and students' background as crucial

factors in promoting foreign language learning, Khansir et al. (2016) conducted a study investigating these variables and their effects on 230 Iranian third-grade students from different socioeconomic levels. The survey questions were related to motivation in general (e.g., Attitude, interest, integrative orientation, etc.). Results showed a positive correlation between motivation and students' social background. Khansir et al. (2016) concluded from their studies that social class can influence students' motivational levels toward learning a foreign language, where parents with a higher economic status could supply their kids with more resources, such as electronic gadgets, computers, going to the theaters, or even traveling to countries where English is the Mother tongue which might increase their level of motivation and even transform it from instrumental to integrative. There is a similarity between this study and the one I am doing, in which both are trying to investigate the role of society, family status, and students' interest in learning a second language as major variables in promoting their motivation toward learning.

In an effort to find constructive ways to prevent demotivation and sustain high motivational levels in students learning a foreign language in North Korea, Tae-Young et al. (2019) conducted a study on 367 sixth-graders. This study has some similarity with the UAE context, since the English language is a required academic subject in schools, and is vital to be accepted in any university. Also, there are excessive social expectations of the students, and an undesirable impact of the immediate learning settings, including teachers' aptitude, teaching methods and materials that are introduced to the students. In their study, Tae-Young et al. (2019) focused on resilience, which is "the ability to bounce back from adversity" (p. 372) as a strong in sustaining motivation for EFL. Resilience plays a large role in preventing school dropout while students are facing challenges such as living in a low-income

environment, and experiencing school/street violence and personal life pressures. According to Tae-Young et al. (2019), demotivation has many faces and it is almost impossible to deal with all the factors that produce demotivation. The best way of fighting it is by nurturing the resilience spirit in our students themselves. They compare it to the L2 motivational self-system that was suggested by Dörnyei in which resilience plays the role of pushing students to reach the “ought to be self.” The results of the study by Tae-Young et al. (2019) showed that “resilience had a significant influence on English proficiency, which passed through EFL learning motivation and EFL learning demotivation, with a standardized coefficient of ($\beta = .17$ $p < .01$)” (p. 384). This is a reminder that teachers are only initiators/guiders and students are the actual creators of their destiny.

Oman, like many other GCC countries, shares lots of cultural similarities with the UAE context, such as the exceeding numbers of expatriates from countries such as the USA, Europe, Philippines, India, etc. According to UAE population and demographics (2020), this was 88% of the overall UAE population. Foreigners have a strong presence in the heart of almost all functions of the country, which has made the English language become the *lingua franca* across the diverse population (Al-Issa, 2014). Even with the importance of English as a communication tool, and the investment of the government in introducing it in the curriculum, students are still not fully or intrinsically motivated toward learning it. Al-Issa (2014) considers a language as a “living entity,” and that it cannot be taught as any other subject. Rather, he argues that it should be incorporated into the daily activities (e.g. reading English magazines, watching English movies, listening to English songs, etc.), which promotes students’ intrinsic motivation, attitudes, and achievement in the target language. Furthermore, the school system is focused mainly on students’ performances at exams, rather than

on true mastery of the language. The fact is that Omani students do not value the English language as a necessity in their lives (Al-Issa, 2014). In an attempt to have a deeper understanding of the lack of motivation within the Omani culture, Al-Issa, (2014) conducted a study using semi-structured interviews on selected grade 12 students and English teachers. He concluded that “ELT theory and practice within the Omani ELT education system are moving in two parallel lines” (p. 415), in which there is not a valid application of most of the studies/theories in the learning process, and that there is an urgent need to close the ideological gap between them.

In an identical environment to the UAE, a study, which was conducted by Eusafzai (2013) on Saudi students in a higher education context, investigating Dörnyei’s L2 Motivational Self-System. The overwhelming cultural and global point of view on the English language is that it is now considered to be the *lingua franca* (Eusafzai, 2013). The data for the study was collected through distributing questionnaires on students in higher education institutions from the Saudi Kingdom and indicated that there are 7 motivational factors presented in Saudi students: “attitude towards learning English, attitude towards L2 people and culture, instrumentality-promotion, the value of studying English, Instrumentality-prevention, parental encouragement, and English anxiety” (Eusafzai, 2013, p. 197). Data analysis on those factors showed that “the mean analysis of the seven factors indicate the highest mean of 5 for both values of studying English and instrumentality-promotion” (p. 196) while running a multiple regression analysis on the data showed that “The strongest weight went to attitude towards learning English, followed by instrumentality-promotion, parental encouragement, value for studying English, instrumentality-prevention, and attitude towards L2 people and culture” (p. 196) (Eusafzai, 2013). This study shows that the Saudi students’ motivation toward

learning the language is mostly for utilitarian/instrumental reasons and that they are protective of their own traditions and focusing on the preservation of their culture, which could be the case with the UAE students as well.

In a study of English language teachers' motivation and techniques, as well as the motivational levels of Saudi students, Alrabai (2014) conducted a study of 36 teachers and 826 students. Two surveys were used in the study to collect data, for both teachers to test their use of motivational techniques, and students their motivational level. The data analysis of the teachers' survey showed that "The mean value of ranged between 2.91 (out of 5) as a minimum value to 3.69 as the maximum value. This indicates that the frequency of motivational techniques used in Saudi EFL classes ranged from rare to occasional" (Alrabai, 2014, p. 234). Meanwhile, the data analysis on students' where a mean of 4 is high, 3 is moderate and less than 3 is low, showed "intrinsic motivation ($M = 3.68$), attitudes toward English language teacher ($M = 3.67$), group cohesiveness ($M=3.60$), linguistic self-confidence ($M=3.51$), motivational intensity ($M=3.14$), which denotes the efforts learners exert in learning the L2 was a low moderately-ranked motivational component" (Alrabai, 2014, p. 239). Alrabai (2014) concluded that teachers have hardly introduced motivational teaching techniques to downplay the feeling of language anxiety among the students and that there was no support for student autonomy, either. The role of the teacher is as important as intrinsic motivation, if not more, due to the strong influence that he/she could have on students, perception of learning, which is shown clearly in this study.

Kuwait environment is parallel to the UAE one, in which they both share the same mother tongue, religious beliefs, lifestyle, and general economic wealth from oil. Fadel Al Othman and Kahled Shuqair are team members in the English Language

Department in the College of Basic Education in Kuwait. Their research found that the main demotivation factor in the English language acquisition is the students' mother tongue, which has a strong pertinence in their history, culture and above all their religion (Othman & Shuqair, 2013). Al-Othman and Shuqair (2013) believe that the current worldwide globalization has obligated the adoption of a single language in the world (which is the English language), and they advocate that there are three components for language acquisition: motivation, positive attitude and a positive learning environment. The problem is that even with all the introduction of up-to-date instruction materials, advanced and innovative teaching models, and the contemporary learning theories, still English learning language suffers due to the salient presence of Western cultural beliefs in it. Al-Othman and Shuqair (2013) consider that another difficulty that the students face in Kuwait is that, primarily, teachers themselves have low levels of motivation toward teaching the language. They concentrate more on teaching the rules of English and mostly neglect the communication part, which is vital for successful language acquisition, since each socio-cultural setting has its own distinctive English language acquisition motivational factors.

The UAE has witnessed overwhelming progress in its economy which had tremendous effects on the culture itself, one of which was the necessity of using the English language as the main medium of communication between the vast number of foreigners that worked in the country and the locals, and which made it a must to obtain the language (Al-sheikh & El-howeris, 2011). According to Al-sheikh and El-howeris (2011), there are a few empirical studies that were conducted on UAE students' motivation toward learning the English language, but no study was conducted on UAE students' motivation toward reading English. Reading is the main

vessel to true education and learning, so they found this odd, and decided to do their study in that area. Their study covered both motivations toward English learning (comprised of intrinsic motivation and attainment value), and English reading (reading-*efficacy*), and included 513 UAE high school students, mixed-gender, and mostly from public schools (Al-sheikh & El-howeris, 2011). A 4-point Likert type scale (Strongly Disagree, Disagree, Agree, and Strongly Agree) survey was introduced to the students, where a multiple-regression analysis was applied to the data. Results indicated that “each predictor separately accounted for the following percentage of motivation to read English: 20.5% by Intrinsic Value of Reading, 16% by Extrinsic Value of Reading, 12% by Attainment Value of Reading, and 10% by Reading *Efficacy*” (Al-sheikh & El-howeris, 2011, p. 5). The study also found that both intrinsic and extrinsic motivation had a significant correlation with the students’ English grades and that their motivation levels to read English were strongly influenced by their reading abilities, interest, and attitudes about the usefulness of the language. These findings are a strong indicator that both intrinsic and extrinsic motivation complement one another in motivating students to learn English, while reading is personal and intrinsically motivates students to read.

One of the few studies on second language acquisition amongst the UAE students, Qashoa (2006) examined students’ integrative and instrumental motivation toward learning English in the UAE. The study was conducted in a public school and around 120 students participated in that study. Results showed that the UAE students have a higher degree of instrumental motivation ($M = 4.15$) compared to integrative motivation ($M = 3.77$), which is typical for most students in the GCC countries, where they view the English language as a tool or a means to achieve higher educational levels or job promotions.

In a study to investigate the role of motivation in second language learning in UAE students (Al-Ta'ani, 2018), investigated the level and the type (instrumental or integrative) of motivation among 50 undergraduate students at the University of Al-Jazeera/Dubai. He concluded that students, in both integrative “average mean scores (3.88)” and instrumental “average mean scores (4.24)” motivation was higher. According to Al-Ta'ani (2018), the reasons why student are more instrumentally motivated is the desire to join a university or obtain a better job in the future, plus extrinsic motivation as government bonus pay for high achieving students.

Motivation and attitude toward second language are like bread and butter: high motivation brings a strong/positive attitude, while low motivation produce negative attitude (Gardner, as cited in Drbseh, 2015). This study was conducted to explore Arab students' (Jordan, Egypt, Saudi and United Arab Emirate) attitudes and motivation toward studying the English language as a foreign language (Drbseh, 2015). Drbseh (2015), in a similar study to Al-Ta'ani (2018), found that the most Arab students have instrumental motivation toward learning the English language as a second language, due to two main factors: a) a personal incentive to gain a better job or a higher incomes, b) a government incentive to develop local scientist, technicians and engineers which will help improve the country's international status and promotes society development to the best. Drbseh's (2015) study tested the attitudes and motivation toward the English language students of Arabic origins from Jordan, Egypt, Saudi and UAE, who were learning in the United Kingdom lead universities. His study showed the following means for motivation for studying English language: Jordanian students ($M = 2.5$, $SD = .48$), Egyptian students ($M = 2.25$, $SD = .50$), Saudi students ($M = 2.5$, $SD = 1.07$) and UAE students ($M = 3.5$, $SD = .40$). This shows stronger motivation by the UAE students to learn the language. Moreover,

attitude toward English instruction amongst the countries showed Jordanian students at ($M = 1.5$, $SD = .86$), Egyptian students ($M = 2.6$, $SD = 1.17$), Saudi students ($M = 2.2$, $SD = .75$) and UAE students ($M = 3.2$, $SD = .41$), which again places the UAE students on the top. Most of this could be linked to the fact that the UAE students come from more prosperous families than the rest of the groups. Drbseh (2015) concluded that students' motivation and attitudes towards learning the English language are mostly determined by the socio-cultural characteristics of each country. Drbseh's study is a reminder of the power of wealth and cultural opening to change as a strong factor in promoting and improving students' motivations and aims toward learning a second language.

CHAPTER 3

METHODOLOGY

This study is an attempt to reach a deeper understanding of students' motivational levels toward academic learning, their attitude toward the usage of English Language in and out of the classroom, and the effect of their immediate environment on their learning process. To accomplish this task, a thorough study covering these elements was undertaken.

Design and Method

A descriptive and correlational design was utilized to help detect the possible factors behind students' strong or weak academic achievement. The data was gathered using self-completion surveys that students would need to answer, which creates less pressure on the students relative to other methods. I also compared their attitudes with their actual school grades. I selected the survey method due to its practicality, where students could answer questions without any outside interference. It is scalable and can be extended easily to a large group of students. Also, it is easy to compare the results statistically with other sources of data such as students' grades.

Population and Study Sample Size

The target population for this study was students attending a government-run high school, which enrolls only local students. This particular school is located in a rural area of Abu Dhabi, the capital of the UAE. This school hosts students from major cities, such as Dubai and Abu Dhabi, as well as students from rural areas. The

sample will include the whole population of the selected school (around 120), which includes students from Grade 6 up to Grade 12. I chose to work with the whole school population since the school represents students from all over the UAE, yet has a small number of students, and because of the willingness of the school administration to supply me with the required records and data.

Instruments

A three-part survey will be distributed among students (see Appendix A), with the intention to examine their attitudes toward education and language learning. The sections include questions about demographic variables, academic motivation, and English language motivation and demotivation.

The demographic section is focused on the unique aspects of the UAE environment. This part of the survey is crucial because it will identify factors that are unique to the UAE's daily lifestyle and may affect academic achievement. Personal factors such as dwelling location (downtown, suburb, or rural area) may encourage or deter academic achievement. Other variables selected include family status (parents' marital status, educational background, and occupation, number of brothers and sisters), as well as the use of medwakh, and private tutoring services.

The second section of my survey uses Njiru's (2003) instrument on Motivation to Achieve Academically. The original instrument had a Cronbach's alpha reliability of .92. Due to the large number of questions that this instrument covers and the fear that the students will lose interest and fail to complete the survey accurately, some subscales of the survey had to be removed (24 questions were removed out of 50), and I kept the parts that cover five important factors in Academic Motivation as shown below in Table 1. After trimming the instrument, reliability testing was conducted on the data collected using R commander, and the results

showed a reliability coefficient of 0.95 for the Goals subscale, 0.97 for the Effort subscale, 0.91 for the Ability subscale, 0.87 for the Extrinsic rewards subscale, and 0.98 for the Intrinsic rewards subscale.

Table 1

Academic Achievement Subscales Retained and Removed

Scales	Retained	Removed	Explanation for removal
Striving for excellence	Goals	Standards	Similar to Goals
	Effort	Tasks Values	Similar to Effort
	Ability		
Desire to learn		Interest Learning From Others Responsibility for Learning	Similar to the Intrinsic section.
Personal incentives	Intrinsic Rewards Extrinsic Rewards	Social Rewards	Mentioned in the Extrinsic section.

The third section of the survey used Al-Sharief's (2013) Motivation/ Demotivation Factors Survey, which is specifically about language learning. The questions are not too many and are not too complicated, yet it covers all aspects of language-learning motivation (Extrinsic, Intrinsic, Introjected, and identified). Questionnaire reliability was calculated using Cronbach's α and the overall reliability coefficient was .72 reflecting an acceptable reliability of the instrument (a reliability test was conducted on the data collected using R commander and the results showed a

reliability coefficient of 0.82 for Motivation subscale, and a 0.74 for Demotivation subscale). Al-Sharief (2013) even added a new aspect of avoidance/rejection, which is common with second language learners. Furthermore, this third section of the survey dealt with five demotivation factors that might increase students' interest in learning language: Language/Culture, Teachers, Environment, Materials, and Methods, which I summed up into two main sections (English Motivation factors, and English Demotivation factors). The complete instrument is found in Appendix A. Note that some of the questions were slightly modified in order to focus solely on student perspectives toward learning the English language.

Data Collection and Analysis

Data needed for this study such as students' grades were supplied by the school itself for the school year 2019-2020. As for the survey, the questions were sent to the school via email to the school administration, who distributed and supervised the process of the students filling out the questionnaires. The whole process happened without any interference from the supervisors, unless clarification is needed.

The data that was collected from this study was statistically analyzed using R Project software, which included descriptive, correlational, ANOVA, and multiple regression analyses.

Ethical Issues

Students were assigned a number, and after data collection and matching of the grades, the researcher received only anonymous information with no reference to their actual names; the random ID number was used up to the point where the grades and surveys had been combined for each student, then even that information will be removed. Also, students' permission to take part in the survey was required with no

pressure from the teacher's side or interference in the process. The actual data that was collected is presented in groups so that anonymity will be preserved and protected, and no individual student can be identified.

CHAPTER 4
DATA ANALYSIS

Chapter 4 is dedicated to analyzing the data that was collected from a government-run high school, which is located in the UAE, and admits only local Emirati youths.

Demographic Analysis

In order to have a better understanding of students' motivational factors in education, we need to first examine their background, such as where they live, family status, and other environmental variables. Demographic data was collected for that purpose and below is the analysis of those questions. A close inspection of the data in Table 2 shows that student enrolment at this particular school starts moderately at Grade 7 (16 students as a start), and then it starts building up in Grade 9, up to Grade 10, to about 25 students per class. Then it starts to decline rapidly by Grades 11 and 12 to around 12 students per class. The significant drop in student numbers during Grades 11 and 12 could be linked to the highly demanding (academically and physically) procedures that the school is putting on students at that class level.

Table 2

Number of Participants per Class

Grades	7	8	9	10	11	12
Number of Participants	16	23	27	27	13	10

Because of the research showing that where students come from may affect their interest in learning, students were asked where they lived. Data showed that most of the students resided outside the city borders, and half of them resided in a rural area (see Figure 5). This interpretation takes into consideration that in the UAE culture/language, a village is a rural area and there is no such thing as a word for “rural area” in their language. Where students live is a crucial factor to take into consideration simply because the rural students are deprived of the modern life that the city provides, such as movie theaters, museums, and the interaction with other cultures. Rural/village dwelling, can be an academic demotivation factor, especially when it comes to learning a foreign language, due to the students’ perception that they don’t really need to learn it. They would not normally have heard English while growing up, and might see no real need for knowing it even as an adult.

Figure 5. Where students live.

Question 2 targeted parental presence in students' lives. Findings showed that almost half of the students (around 45%) do not live with both parents, as shown in Figure 6. This is somehow typical to the UAE culture, due to polygamy where men can have up to four wives, and due to the high level of divorces. Parents are important in raising, protecting, educating and motivating children, and the absence of one of them can have a negative effect on the children. According to Park (2008), who conducted a study on single parenting and its effects on children's education, students' aspiration for education is lesser in a single parent household, as well as with an increased number of siblings in one family.

Figure 6. Who students live with.

The size of a family can have side effects on students' motivation (Park, 2008). That is why this study examined the number of siblings that students have.

Figure 7 shows that around 80% of the students have a large family size of eleven or more siblings. Large numbers of children can hinder parents' abilities to give the necessary parental care and directions that the children rely upon to face obstacles in their academic endeavors (Feng, 2020). The same study by Feng (2020) concluded that "Muslim children are significantly negatively impacted by expanded sibling size" (p. 22).

Figure 7. Number of siblings in the student's family.

A demographic question targeted the usage of the medwakh by students (medwakh is a smoking apparatus that resembles a small pipe that is used heavily by most of the Emirati youth). The data showed that 72% claim to never use it (see Figure 8), while 22% use it occasionally, and a small number of students (around 6%) are high users of this harmful habit.

In the next question about how many of their close friends use the medwakh, however, the answers showed that almost 76% have friends that are regular users, and this is quite confusing. How can a boarding school have only 6% of its students using medwakh, while three-quarters of students' friends are smokers? Logically, this is a strong indication that the data regarding smoking is highly questionable and not reliable. One of the main reasons for students to cover their addiction to smoking medwakh by not answering the questions related to using medwakh is the strict school rules and regulations against such a bad habit. According to a study by Al-Houqani et al. (2018), "A study on high school students in Dubai reported that 72.1% of students have used tobacco during their lifetime" (p. 7) which is another reason that drives me to believe that students are not forthcoming in the question regarding smoking.

Figure 8. Students' dependence on smoking medwakh.

The students filled out the surveys used in this study under supervision in a school setting. However, some of the data collected are questionable, when compared to my ten years' experience working with these students. One example of this is their reported activities after school, where 86% of the students answered that they spent their time working on their school homework, which I doubt.

Private tutoring is a large and lucrative business and is widely spread in schools all over the UAE. One of the survey questions examined the number of students that said they were dependent on private tutoring. The collected data related to this question shows that a large number of students have solicited private tutoring (none of the students are totally dependent on private tutoring), and only around 21% don't rely on it (see Figure 9). Private tutoring can be a blessing in promoting and improving students' self-efficacy and increasing their knowledge in the subject matter, or it could be only directed into passing exams, especially if the private tutor is their school teacher.

Figure 9. Students who take private tutoring lessons.

Two other questions were presented that were related to the subject of tutoring. Students were asked if private lessons were helpful. Around 67% of the students said that they believe that private tutoring does not help a lot. When asked about the background of the tutor, responses showed that over 63% of the private tutors are from a different school (See Figure 10). According to my own personal experience with the students at this school, I am inclined to believe that the opposite is true. They might not have reported this, however, due to the fact that it is forbidden by law for teachers to tutor their own school students, yet many teachers are involved in private tutoring due to the lucrative benefits that it brings. When they tutor their students, they usually focus almost exclusively on helping students pass the exam. Many studies have dealt with this phenomenon.

Figure 10. Private tutor backgrounds.

One study conducted by Farah (2011), addresses the increasing number of students who are dependent on private tutoring (almost 73% of male students rely on private tutoring). Farah's (2011) study concluded that: 1) most teachers are engaging in private tutoring to improve financially and for job insecurities. 2) School teachers encourage their students to take private lessons, and 52.0% of private tutors are student's school teachers. 3) Students blame the overall educational system for their reliance on private lessons. 4) Private tutors are breaking the school code of ethics by teaching their students. 5) Classroom teaching quality is negatively affected due to private tutoring, and tutoring is usually directed toward students passing exams.

Descriptive Statistics on Motivation and Grades

Prior to analyzing the relationships between motivation, grades, and demographic variables, we need to examine students' grade average levels, their English grade average, their academic motivation levels, and their motivation toward learning English. This section will examine all of these factors from the data collected from the survey.

Table 3 below presents student's academic averages per class, as well as their English averages, with the standard deviation for each class as well. From the data received, students' overall averages start at medium high levels of 74.3 in Grade 7, and then start to gradually decline up till Grade 10. A minor improvement is detected during Grades 10 and 11, which is followed by a significant increase in Grade 12 as shown in Figure 11 below. The standard deviation shows that Grade 12 has the lowest variability, while Grade 11 has the highest standard deviation, showing that some students do well, but others do very poorly (see Figure 11).

Table 3

Students' Academic and English Averages

Grade	Academic average		English average	
	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>
7	74.3	18.1	75.6	23.7
8	68.4	14.8	68.0	15.2
9	67.4	14.6	67.5	19.1
10	67.7	15.8	65.7	18.0
11	69.8	20.3	67.8	25.1
12	78.1	9.2	75.0	9.3

Figure 11. Students' academic averages per class.

This variation in student averages could be linked to the sudden transition from public/private schools into government-run schools, where students are coming with a positive attitude and high expectations at Grade 7, then, later on, the environmental pressure in the new school takes its toll on them. From Grade 10 and up, students grow older and get more mature and capable of better controlling their

progress, which is visible in the increase in their overall grade averages, especially in Grade 12 where they are expecting to graduate.

The situation is almost identical with students' English language averages as shown in Figure 12 below. The English overall average starts high at Grade 7 and then declines up to Grades 11 and 12. In Grades 11 and 12, the English average starts to improve. This may be due to their maturity and their eagerness to graduate high school (see Table 3). The standard deviation score is high for Grade 7. This could be linked to the diversity of students that are coming from different schools and cities. But what is peculiar are the levels of standard deviation in Grade 11, which should be lower.

My assumptions are that at Grade 11, some students are drained, emotionally and intellectually, from the elevated school educational requirement pressures, and some might even be planning to move to a different school. Grade 11 is also when the school puts extra pressure on the students to filter out the unsuitable ones. In any case, it is clear that English grades follow the same pattern as other grades, simply because the English language is the medium for lecturing in most school subjects. A study (Stoffelsma & Spooren, 2019) measured the effects of English reading on students' overall GPA in a bilingual setting, where the majority of the subjects are presented in English. The results showed that there was a significant relationship between English reading test results and academic achievement, and that reading is a strong indicator of students' English proficiency.

Figure 12. Students' English averages per class.

The data collected from students to measure their academic motivation levels used a 5-point Likert scale ranging from 1 = Strongly Agree to 5 = Strongly Disagree. The questions were targeted to measure five factors of academic motivation: students' educational goals, students' cognitive abilities, students' stamina in facing and overcoming educational obstacles, their intrinsic drive to learn, and the extrinsic motive to achieve academically.

The data collected from the survey showed that almost all students set high Goals in relation to education, and they claimed to be giving it most of their effort to accomplish those goals. As for abilities, the survey data also showed a high perception of ability from the students' side, and that they are highly motivated intrinsically, as well as extrinsically (see Table 4 below).

What is intriguing in Table 4 is that most students have their answers mostly in the Strongly Agree column (Total Academic Motivation $M = 1.14$, or Strongly Agree), which is highly unusual, especially for the type of students that the study is targeting. I worked with those students for around 10 years and I noticed that most of

them manifested a low level of academic motivation. My guess is that either they did not take the survey seriously, or there was some other force at work there.

Table 4

Students' Academic Motivation by Grade

Academic Motivation \ Grade	7	8	9	10	11	12	All Grades
Goals	1.06	1.04	1.24	1.10	1.37	1.04	1.14
Effort	1.06	1.05	1.23	1.10	1.34	1.06	1.14
Ability	1.06	1.07	1.26	1.07	1.35	1.13	1.16
Extrinsic	1.06	1.06	1.26	1.10	1.31	1.07	1.14
Intrinsic	1.02	1.00	1.22	1.11	1.21	1.08	1.11
Total Academic Motivation	1.05	1.05	1.26	1.10	1.32	1.09	1.14

A similar scale was used to obtain information regarding student motivation/demotivation levels toward English language. A quick look at the data suggests that most answers were in the Strongly Agree section as they were in the academic motivational data. However, this data showed that most students were closer to the Agree section with a mean of 1.88 for the English Motivation levels. The Demotivation level questions were similar to the academic motivational ones ($M = 1.43$) which is quite visible in Table 5.

Table 5

Students' English Motivational/Demotivation Levels by Grade

Grades	7	8	9	10	11	12	All Grades
English Motivation	1.88	1.75	1.89	1.80	2.26	1.39	1.88
English Demotivation	1.24	1.39	1.23	1.24	1.63	1.85	1.43

Differences Based on Demographic Variables

ANOVA was used to establish any significant differences between selected demographic variables in comparison with students' academic average, English average, academic motivation, and English motivation/demotivation levels.

The demographic question examining where students reside (downtown, suburb, or village), was statistically analyzed with students' average grades. The data results also showed that more than half of the students live in the villages, around 40% live in the suburbs, and only around 13% of them live in the city. The results showed a statistically significant difference ($df = 2, F = 4.895, p = 0.01^{**}$). Data (see Table 6) showed that students living downtown had a significantly higher academic average, in comparison with students living outside the city. In a similar manner, students residing in the suburbs had significantly higher averages ($M = 72.13$) than those who lived in the village ($M = 65.27$) (as shown in Figure 13).

Table 6

Students' Averages in Comparison with their Residential Status.

Dwelling Status	Downtown	Suburb	Village/Rural area
Mean	77.56	72.13	65.27
Standard Deviation	17.79	14.29	15.41
Number of Students (%)	16 (13.8%)	48 (41.4%)	52 (44.8%)

$n = 116$

This phenomenon could be linked to many factors, such as the exposure that the city can provide to the students in many areas, the economic status of the family, in a way that living downtown requires a more prosperous family to be able to do so, simply because housing is far more expensive in comparison to the other areas. One

other recent study (UK Essays, 2018) found that students who are living in the cities will have a higher exposure to intellectual events, which promote better academic achievement, whereas in a village, the opposite is true.

Figure 13. Student's averages by dwelling location.

Students' dwelling location was also compared against their English averages using ANOVA. The results were statistically significant, as well ($F = 3.708$, $p = 0.0138^*$). Figure 14 shows the same results as with academic averages. The same factors as discussed previously in regards to students dwelling and their academic averages could be applied here as well.

Figure 14. Student's English averages by dwelling location.

When examining students' dwelling conditions to their academic motivation levels and their English motivation/demotivation levels, no significant differences were detected. This could be due to the behavior of most of the students while answering questions that were related to motivation, which resulted in almost universally high scores on all of the motivation measures. Because of these high scores, there is little space for differentiation by any demographic variables. The rest of the results of the demographic questions also showed no significant differences when compared to student academic averages, English averages or English motivation levels.

The parental status of the students—if they live with both parents, one parent or with someone else—showed that students who are living with both parents or with their mother had a higher academic average (both parents $M = 71$, mothers $M = 70$) while the ones that are living with their father had the lowest (fathers $M = 57$, other $M = 60$) as shown in Figure 15 below. Even though these values did not reach the level of statistical significance, they still show the normal pattern that would be expected, based on the literature.

Figure 15. Student's parental status.

The data on the students' family size and their academic average also did not reach the level of statistical significance. Still, it showed that students with an average number of siblings (between one and 10) had a higher academic average ($M = 75$) than those who had a larger family size ($M = 67$) as shown in Figure 16 below.

Figure 16. Student’s family size and their academic average.

Another interesting finding was in question number 9, which investigated the students' dependence on private lessons, and the data analysis had shown that those who used private tutors ($M = 70$) had a slightly better average than students who never used private tutoring ($M = 66$) as shown in Figure 17 below. No statistical significance was found, as the difference was too small.

Figure 17. Student’s dependency on private tutoring.

Academic Average and Motivation

In order to measure the relationship between students’ academic average, their English average, and their academic motivation and English motivation levels, Pearson’s Product-Moment Correlation was used. The correlation results (as shown in Table 7 below) indicate that there is a moderate negative relationship between students’ overall academic average and both academic and English motivation, which is strikingly unusual. This means that as their motivation goes up, their grades actually go down. This is not normal, and does not match with other research. It could be linked to the careless way in which the surveys were filled out, which I address in

the next chapter. Almost the same negative correlation was detected between the students' average English Demotivation. The same correlation test was done on students' averages in English and their motivational level results were very similar to the previous test, as shown in Table 8 below. This result is not like other research that I have read, and may be related to the way students apparently filled in the data inaccurately (the responses were almost entirely either 1s or 5s for the entire dataset). Only the demographic data appeared to be somewhat more accurate.

Table 7

Correlation between Students' Academic Average and Motivation

	Academic Motivation	English Motivation	English Demotivation
Pearson's r	-0.260	-0.488	-0.265
p-value	0.005	0.000	0.000
N	116	116	116

Table 8

Correlation between Students' English Averages and Motivation

	Academic Motivation	English Motivation	English Demotivation
Pearson's r	-0.265	-0.488	-0.584
p-value	0.002	0.000	0.000
N	116	116	116

What is worth mentioning here is that, even though it was not in my study's targeted questions, while conducting a correlational analysis test between students' academic grades averages and their English averages, I found a strong positive correlation between them (The Pearson's r is = 0.92). That is clearly obvious in Figure 18 below, which is a strong indicator that the English language has a profound relationship with students' grades. This may suggest that students who are academically high achievers score high in the English language. Alternatively, the better they are in English, the higher their academic grades are. It is worth mentioning again that the English language can be linked to their academic achievement simply because most of the subjects are taught in English, except Civics, Religion, and Arabic. Because of this, the most likely scenario is that English ability affects their other subject grades, but a correlational study cannot determine causation.

Figure 18. A visual correlation between students' average and their English average.

CHAPTER 5

CONCLUSION

The aim of this study was to investigate students' academic motivation levels, as well as the degree of motivation to learn English. The answers showed that most of the students scored high levels of motivation in all aspects (goals, abilities, efforts, intrinsic and extrinsic factors), while their overall averages (for most of them) were not really as high as they were supposed to be. This raised serious questions regarding the accuracy and honesty that the students employed while answering the question related to motivation. Due to this fact, I have an obligation not to continue analyzing the data related to motivation in this study, so I did not conduct the planned multiple regression.

Demographic Influence on Student's Academic Averages

Even with the fact that some responses seemed to be inaccurate, a large part of the demographical questions seemed to be reliable, except the ones that were related to smoking medwakh or to if the private tutor is from their school. I think that students were concerned that both of these questions could be used against them by the school, since smoking is forbidden and students who are caught smoking will be expelled from school. Whereas it is against the UAE laws for teachers to teach their students, this also might make students reluctant to give a straight answer in that area, as well.

Still, some of the data could be used, such as students' grades (which are from the school administration), and some selected demographic questions. These proved

to be useful in linking some variables in the students' environment to their academic performance. One of the key findings is that the student's residential location plays a significant role in their overall school average. Students that live in the city have significantly higher averages, in overall grades and in English grades, compared to students living in places far from the city. Many factors play a role in that area, such as the exposure to many educational places/events, such as museums, forums, and theaters. Also, they have higher chances of meeting other cultures, which played a role in encouraging students to communicate in the English language, and so on.

Another demographical question worth mentioning is the student's parental status, which showed that students who lived with both parents, or with their biological mother had higher grades in comparison to the ones who lived only with their fathers or with neither of their parents. This finding shows the importance of the positive role that parents play in student's educational endeavors, and that mothers are more concerned in that matter because most mothers in the UAE are housewives, which gives them ample opportunities to nurture their kids, and support them educationally.

This study showed that student averages were higher for students with a family size of ten children or less, in comparison to students who have more than ten siblings in the family. Obviously, the larger the number of children, the harder is it on parents to monitor them effectively, or support them educationally.

The last finding is that students who had a private tutor scored a little higher than the ones who did not. I would have expected this finding to have a wider, significant difference between them, especially when most of their private tutors are actual teachers, but the results showed only insignificant differences. My main aim behind this particular question was to find out if the private tutor was actually their

school teacher (which I have observed is generally the case), and if the private lessons are only aiming at making the students pass their exam, but students did not give a clear answer in that area.

Answers to the Research Questions

The data collected answered the research questions as follows:

1. What are the levels of student academic motivation, motivation /demotivation toward learning English (the language of study), and the level of academic achievement during one academic school year?

No direct correlation was detected between students' averages and their academic/English motivational levels, which could be linked to irresponsible responses to the question, or lack of interest in it. Levels of motivation were reported as extremely high, which also does not match what is generally observed and reported.

2. Are there significant differences in students' English language motivation, academic motivation, and overall academic achievement based on selected demographic variables?

The study showed that where students live may have a direct effect on their averages, as well as the number of siblings that they have, or if they are living with only their father, or someone who is not their parent.

3. Is there a significant relationship between students' level of motivation and overall academic achievement? Between English language motivation/demotivation and academic achievement?

A small to medium negative correlation was detected between students' academic averages and their academic/English motivation. This negative correlation suggests that when motivational levels increase, students' grades

go down, or vice versa, which is not the case in other similar studies. It also does not make sense that more motivated students get lower grades. This unusual result could be related to the students randomly answering the survey questions, which was also evident from the way the papers were filled out, with mostly 1 or 5 as answers.

4. What is the best model for academic achievement that can be built using the variables from this study?

No correlation was detected between students' averages and their motivation levels, which prevented me from conducting a multi-regression analysis.

Implications

The bottom line of these findings is that even though students said they were motivated, they were clearly not academically motivated enough to get good grades, as shown by their academic averages as well as their English average. The reason/reasons behind that could range from the fact that almost 85% of the students reside outside the cities (41% live in the suburbs, and 44% in the villages), and are living in secluded areas, where they are deprived of direct contact with other cultures, and their intellectual exposure may be limited to outings into the desert, or sitting with friends and relatives around a fire, chatting. Another problem that the students are facing is the large number of siblings, living without a father figure, the use of private lesson by teachers as mean of financial gain instead of helping students grow academically, and the overall culture that sees the English language as a means to detach them from their Arabic/Islamic roots.

Even though almost all of the students answered their questionnaires with a positive attitude towards motivations, the truth of the matter is that students are in dire need of extrinsic factors to empower them to aim higher in their academic endeavors.

Money, presents and material factors may not work well with them, due to the fact that most of the students are living within families that are financially secure.

Therefore, effective motivational factors should probably come in the shape of emotional and intellectual support.

Recommendations

Recommendations for Parents

Someone once said that it takes the whole village to raise a child. This may mean that students' educational motivation can be linked to many factors. One important factor in the equation is their parents, due to the profound influence that they can have on their children's education. Below are some recommendations that are possible for parents to implement would include the following:

1. Parents should be encouraged to get seriously involved in their children's education, especially if they are single parents. The data showed that if students are living with both parents or only with their mothers, they do better in school.
2. Living in the city seems to improve students' academic achievement. We cannot simply ask the family to move from wherever they are living into the city. Parents should be encouraged, however to motivate their children to participate in any event (even if it is outside the area that they are living in) that might promote their intellectual abilities and English communication skills. Parents could send their children to a boarding school in the city, and encourage them to be open and accepting to other cultures as equals to theirs. After all, education is not just a book and a pencil, it is life, and the way we interact with our surroundings, and students should live it to the fullest.

3. Also, the study has shown that many of the students' friends are using medwakh, and the best prevention for that bad habit starts at home. Parents should refrain from using the medwakh (at least in front of their kids) and be particular about their children's friends, especially the ones that smoke medwakh, due to the serious damage that it could cause on both the lungs as well as the brain (not to mention the other health hazards).

Recommendations for Emirati Schools

Emirati schools have many challenges to overcome. Some key challenges are that the teachers come from a different cultural /ethnic background, and the English language is used as the main medium of teaching. My recommendations are for the specific school under study, but other Emirati schools might also benefit from considering these recommendations:

1. The school and its teachers must focus more on promoting academic motivation in their students by any means, so that they will be driven into learning. This could include promoting self-efficacy in their students, encouraging them to have dreams and goals (especially futuristic ones which could be accomplished). Students' motivation is no easy task that is why it is vital that the school invest in improving its teachers' capabilities in motivating students through professional development sessions, seminars, lectures, and any other activities that might enhance their capabilities in motivating their students to excel in education.
2. This study has shown a strong correlation between the level of English achievement and their grade point average. This shows the English language to be a profound factor in improving students' academic achievement. Schools should promote the usage of the English language at

all times during school hours. They should try to gain students' attention to the language by using computer educational games (for lower grades), showing upper classes English movies without subtitles, and any other activity that is fun to do yet requires the use of the English language.

3. Private lessons which includes teachers teaching their own school students is forbidden by law all over the UAE, yet they are happening on a regular basis. Schools should not be lenient in this area, and must enforce this rule by whatever means necessary. Data here suggested that tutoring does not significantly raise students' grades. Meanwhile, studies on private tutoring have suggested that it could have negative effects on teachers' teaching abilities due to the extra time that they are spending in private tutoring.
4. This study shows that when the parents are supporting their children, their grades improve. For that reason, parents have to be encouraged by the school to become more involved in their children's educational journey. Meetings between parents and teachers should occur on a regular basis, so that parents are aware of their child's weaknesses as soon as they are detected.

Recommendations for Further Research

The main target of this study was to investigate students' academic/English motivational levels of the students, yet, the data presented have yielded some unexpected and nonsensical results. If I had the opportunity to do the same study again, I would rather do one-on-one private interviews with each student instead of a questionnaire. The advantage of an interview is the ability to personally interact with the students, and the higher opportunity to gain students' trust, which would encourage them to be more open in their answers.

I would also like to investigate the factors that cause students living in the city to perform academically better than the ones that live outside of the city. Again, I would do this using private interviews. What we could learn could be opposite to what other studies have shown, especially since no study like this has been conducted in the GCC.

Finally, I have witnessed through personal observation that most students dislike the English language and have a negative attitude towards learning it. This in itself is worth exploring, especially in the UAE context, due to the growing usage of the English language in all schools, and the fact that English is becoming a major factor of deciding if students can proceed to university or not.

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APPENDIX

STUDENT QUESTIONNAIRE

This survey is anonymous. Please do not write your name, or any other comments that will make you identifiable on it. By completing this survey, you are consenting to take part in this research, which is intended to have a better understanding of attitude toward learning and if they are enthusiastic about being a high achievers in education.

Demographic Variables. Instructions. This section of the survey is custom made for GCC students to have a better understanding about their lifestyle out of school and their attitude toward private lessons and the role of money in their lives.

<p>1. I live:</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Downtown <input type="checkbox"/> In the suburbs <input type="checkbox"/> In a village <input type="checkbox"/> In a rural area</p>
<p>2. I live with:</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Both parents <input type="checkbox"/> Father <input type="checkbox"/> Mother <input type="checkbox"/> Other</p>
<p>3. My father's work:</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Owns a business <input type="checkbox"/> Government employee <input type="checkbox"/> Private employee <input type="checkbox"/> Unemployed</p>
<p>4. The number of children in my family:</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> < 5 <input type="checkbox"/> 5-10 <input type="checkbox"/> 11-15 <input type="checkbox"/> > 15</p>
<p>5. How many of your immediate family members have a university degree?</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> 0 <input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> Between 5 and 10 <input type="checkbox"/> More than 10</p>
<p>6. I use the evening after school to:</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Work on my school homework <input type="checkbox"/> Watch TV <input type="checkbox"/> Hang out with friends in the desert until morning <input type="checkbox"/> Sit in Al Majlis with friends/family all night</p>
<p>7. I use medwakh:</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Never <input type="checkbox"/> Sometimes <input type="checkbox"/> A lot <input type="checkbox"/> All of the time</p>
<p>8. How many of your friends use medwakh?</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> None of my friends <input type="checkbox"/> Less than 5 <input type="checkbox"/> Between 5 and 10 <input type="checkbox"/> More than 10</p>
<p>9. I have a private tutor helping me with my studies:</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Never took lessons <input type="checkbox"/> Sometimes <input type="checkbox"/> A lot <input type="checkbox"/> All of the time</p>
<p>10. Private lessons help me: (if you never had a private tutor, go to Question 12)</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Do not help me at all <input type="checkbox"/> Pass the exams <input type="checkbox"/> Understand the lessons better <input type="checkbox"/> Improve my academic skills</p>
<p>11. My private tutor is: (if you never had a private tutor, go to Question 12)</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> One of my parents <input type="checkbox"/> A relative <input type="checkbox"/> My teacher <input type="checkbox"/> A teacher from another school.</p>

Motivation to Achieve Academically

Instructions: Please check the appropriate box to indicate your opinion about each statement.

A = in ALL of my studies M = in MOST of my studies F = in FEW of my studies
N = in NONE of my studies

		A	M	F	N
Goals					
1	I try different ways to solve academic (study) problems.				
2	I set realistic and challenging academic (study) goals.				
3	I set highest academic goals, which I can achieve.				
4	When I do not get what I expect in my studies, I work hard to so that I may achieve my goals.				
5	If I do not attain my goals, I try again and again.				
Effort					
6	I make strong demand on myself to pass my studies.				
7	I struggle hard to get correct answers in homework given.				
8	I check my work carefully so that I can get good marks.				
9	I prepare myself to get high marks in my studies.				
10	I make strong effort to achieve as high marks as I can.				
11	When I have no enough time for studies, I think about the importance of education.				
12	I value achievement (passing) in studies.				
Ability					
13	I have confidence that I can pass my studies.				
14	I receive encouragement on my studies from my teachers.				
15	I receive encouragement from at least one friend on my ability in my studies.				
16	I receive encouragement from at least one of my parents on my ability in studies.				
Extrinsic Rewards					
17	I like the rewards that studies bring.				
18	I try to work hard because doing well in studies brings high status.				
19	I like to study in order to be the winner in my class.				
Intrinsic Rewards					
20	I like studies because we interact with friends while we study.				
21	I try to work hard in studies because of the challenges it brings.				
22	I like the intellectual challenge brought about by academic work.				
23	I like to solve problems in studies.				

Note. This instrument was adapted and used with permission from Joseph N. Njiru. (2003). *Measuring academic motivation to achieve for high school students using a Rasch measurement model* (MA thesis). Retrieved from <https://ro.ecu.edu.au/theses/1320>

Motivation/Demotivation Factors

Instructions: Please check the appropriate box to indicate your opinion about each statement.

SA = Strongly Agree A = Agree N = Neutral D = Disagree SD = Strongly Disagree

Statement		SA	A	N	D	SD
1	English is a difficult language.					
2	I always have a good relationship with my English teacher.					
3	I will learn English better had I learned it in an English language environment.					
4	I don't find difficulty studying my English textbooks.					
5	I often get help with my language mistakes in English classes.					
6	Learning English is very important to me.					
7	Most teachers who taught me English are not qualified.					
8	English classrooms do not represent suitable language learning environments.					
9	English learning materials rely more on memorization than on thinking.					
10	I often enjoy the methods used in teaching English.					
11	One important use of learning English is knowing about the Western culture.					
12	I like my English teachers.					
13	We use technology in fun ways in English language classes.					
14	English materials are often above my level.					
15	Learning English is similar to the learning of most theoretical subjects.					
16	Learning English should be restricted to save our Islamic identity and Arabic language.					
17	Most English teachers do not help students love learning the language.					
18	My classmates in English classes do not contribute in making learning the language more enjoyable.					
19	The reading texts and exercises in English learning materials are mostly boring.					
20	I find a lot of opportunity in English classes to practice the language.					
21	Learning English is a necessity these days.					
22	I would have learned English better had my teachers been native speakers of English.					
23	More time is needed in English classrooms to learn the language better.					
24	Most exercises and practices we perform in English classrooms are not really useful in learning the language.					
25	Most teaching methods of English do not help students apply what they have learned.					

Note. From Al-Sharief, S. N. (2013, January 1). The Interplay of Motivation and Demotivation: The Case of EFL Learners Majoring in English. *International Journal of Applied Linguistics & English Literature*, 2(1), 53-59. doi:10.7575/ijalel.v.2n.1p.53. Used with permission.

CURRICULUM VITAE

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Educational Background

2018-2021 Master of Arts in Education, Middle East University
2002-2004 MCSE (Microsoft Certified System Engineer)
1998-1999 Diploma in computer programming, Database and Internet solution Developer
1984-1988 Bachelor of Arts, Business Administration, Beirut, Lebanon

Work Experience

2008-2018 ICT Lead teacher, Student Life Organizer and Academic Quality Coordinator,
with SABIS in the UAE
2005-2007 ICT Teacher, and IT Admin. at GBES school in Ashrafieh, Lebanon
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